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INDO AMERICAN
JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL
RESEARCH

Matrix Tablets as Controlled drug delivery systems

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ARTICLE INFO

Received 22 July 2011
Received in revised form 21
August 2011
Accepted 25 September 2011
Available online October 2011

Keywords

Controlled released,
Matrix tablets,
monolithic devices,
polymers.

ABSTRACT

From the point of patient compliance, dosage regimen of an orally administered drug may be considered to be optional when the therapeutic effects are maintained for the desired duration of the treatment at the lowest frequency of administration. The development of delivery system from which the active substance is released at a passively controlled release rate over an extended period of time. One of the most rational ways to increase the therapeutic efficacy of drugs consists in creating their ready to use forms with controlled release, which allows the desired therapeutic effects by reduced number of drug intakes, thus decrease the level of toxicity and risk of side effects. The modern ready-to-use medicinal forms for per oral administration with controlled drug release include matrix tablets.

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Please cite this article in press as: Kiran Kumar.S et al., Matrix Tablets as Controlled drug delivery systems. Indo American Journal of Pharm Research. 2011;1(4):343-350.

INTRODUCTION:

Matrix type oral controlled drug delivery systems are most common of the monolithic devices for controlling the release of drugs. Reason for this, they were relatively easy to fabricate compared to other devices and no danger of accidental dose dumping compared reservoir devices. In these devices the active agent is present as dispersion with in the polymer matrix and is compressed. The drug release properties of monolithic devices are depends on initial concentration of drug in the matrix, solubility of the drug, presence of water-soluble additives, wetting of drug, porosity, tortuosity and polymer system forming the matrix^{1,2,3}.

The incorporation of an active compound in a matrix formulations are irrational in case of,

- Large doses
- Long biological half-lives
- Very potent drugs
- Irregularly or poorly absorbed drugs
- Drugs which do not show relationship between blood levels and biological activity

Matrix system

A matrix system consists of active and inactive ingredients that are homogeneously dispersed and mixed in the dosage form. It is by far the most commonly used oral controlled release technology and the popularity of the matrix systems can be attributed to several factors which will be discussed in the later section^{4,5,6}. The release from matrix type formulations governed by Fick's first law of diffusion. J is flux, or rate of diffusion, while Q is the amount diffused per unit of time t , and D is diffusion coefficient.

$$J = \frac{dQ}{dt} = -D \frac{dC}{dx}$$

Advantages of Matrix Tablets

Therapy

- Uniform blood-drug concentration/response
- Reduction of adverse reaction occurrence
- Improved patient compliance
- Can be made to release high molecular weight compounds

Economy

- Less expensive daily treatment

- Decreased costs of nursing time
- Better drug utilization

Different fronts of a swellable matrix tablet

- A Undissolved Drug, Glassy Polymer Layer
- B Undissolved Drug, Gel Layer
- C Dissolved Drug, Gel Layer

Disadvantages of Matrix Tablets^{7,8}

- Loss of flexibility in dosage.
- After the drug release from dosage form, the remaining matrix must be removed.
- Release rate continuously diminishes due to an increase in diffusional resistance and/or a decrease in effective area at the diffusion front.
- A substantial sustained effect may produce through the use of very slow release rates.
- The first order drug delivery mechanism i.e. release rate drug decreases proportionally over time may causes the changing surface area and drug diffusional path length with time.

POLYMERS USED IN MATRIX TABLETS

Hydrogels - Polyhydroxyethyl methacrylate (PHEMA), Cross-linked polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), Cross-linked Polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), Polyethylene oxide (PEO), Polyacrylamide (PA).

Soluble polymers - Polyethylene glycol (PEG), Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), Polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP), Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC).

Biodegradable polymers - Polylactic acid (PLA), Polyglycolic acid (PGA), Polycaprolactone (PCL), Polyanhydrides, Polyorthoesters.

Nonbiodegradable polymers - Polyethylene vinyl acetate (PVA), Polydimethyl siloxane (PDS), Polyether urethane (PEU), Polyvinyl chloride (PVC), Cellulose acetate (CA), Ethyl cellulose (EC).

Mucoadhesive polymers - Polycarbophil, Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, Polyacrylic acid, Tragacanth Methyl cellulose, Pectin.

Natural gums - Xanthan gum, Guar gum, Karaya gum.

TYPES OF MATRIX SYSTEMS

The matrix system can be divided into two categories depending on the types of retarding agent or polymeric materials^{9,10,11}.

(a) Hydrophobic matrix system

This is the only system where the use of polymer is not essential to provide controlled drug release, although insoluble polymers have been used. As the term suggests, the primary rate-controlling components of hydrophobic matrix are water insoluble in nature. These ingredients include waxes, glycerides and polymeric materials such as ethyl cellulose, methyl cellulose and acrylate copolymer¹².

To modulate drug release, it may be necessary to incorporate soluble ingredients such as lactose into formulation. The presence of insoluble ingredient in the formulations helps to maintain the physical dimension of hydrophobic matrix during drug release. As such, diffusion of active ingredient from the system is the release mechanism, and the corresponding release characteristic can be described by Higuchi equation known as square root of time release kinetic (Higuchi, 1963). The square root of time release profile is expected with a porous monolith, where the release from such system is proportional to the drug loading. In addition, hydrophobic matrix systems generally are not suitable for insoluble drug because the concentration gradient is too low to render adequate drug release^{13,14}.

As such, depending on actual ingredient properties or formulation design, incomplete drug release

within the gastrointestinal transit time is a potential risk and need to be delineated during the development. With the growing needs for optimization of therapy, matrix systems providing programmable rates of delivery become more important. Constant rate delivery always has been one of the primary targets of controlled release system especially for drug with narrow therapeutic index^{15,16}.

(b) Hydrophilic matrix system

The primary rate limiting ingredients of hydrophilic matrix are polymers that would swell on contact with aqueous solution and form a gel layer on the surface of the system. When the release medium (i.e. water) is thermodynamically compatible with a polymer, the solvent penetrates into the free spaces between macromolecular chains. The polymer may undergo a relaxation process, due to the stress of the penetrated solvent, so that the polymer chains become more flexible and the matrix swells. This allows the encapsulated drug to diffuse more rapidly out of the matrix. On the other hand, it would take more time for drug to diffuse out of the matrix since the diffusion path is lengthened by matrix swelling. Moreover, it has been widely known that swelling and diffusion are not the only factors that determine the rate of drug release^{17,18}.

For dissolvable polymer matrix, polymer dissolution is another important mechanism that can modulate the drug delivery rate. While either swelling or dissolution can be the predominant factor for a specific type of polymers, in most cases drug release kinetics is a result of a combination of these two mechanisms. The enhanced motility of the polymeric chain favours the transport of dissolved drug. Polymer relaxation phenomena determine the swelling or volume increase of the matrix. Depending on the polymer characteristics, the polymer amount in the rubbery phase, at the surface of the matrix, could reach the disentanglement concentration; the gel layer varies in thickness and the matrix dissolves or erodes^{19,10}.

The concentration at which polymeric chains can be considered disentangled was demonstrated to correspond to an abrupt change in the rheological

properties of the gel. Swelling controlled release systems are based upon these principles. Due to the viscoelastic properties of the polymer which are enhanced by the presence of cross-linked network, anomalous penetrant transport can be observed. Transport can be reduced to three driving forces. The penetrant concentration gradient, polymer concentration gradient and osmotic force behavior are observed as a result of polymer network. Appropriate polymer can counterbalance normal Fickian diffusion by hindering the release of embedded drug, leading to an extended period of drug delivery, and possibly zero-order release^{21,22}.

Drug Release from Matrix systems

Drug in the outside layer exposed to the bathing solution is dissolved first and then diffuses out of the matrix. This process continues with the interface between the bathing solution and the solid drug moving toward the interior. It follows that for this system to be diffusion controlled, the rate of dissolution of drug particles within the matrix must be much faster than the diffusion rate of dissolved drug leaving the matrix^{23,24}.

Derivation of the mathematical model to describe this system involves the following assumptions:

- a) A pseudo-steady state is maintained during drug release;
- b) The diameter of the drug particles is less than the average distance of drug diffusion through the matrix;
- d) The bathing solution provides sink conditions at all times.

The release behaviour for the system can be mathematically described by the following equation:

$$dM/dh = Co \cdot dh - Cs/2 \text{ (Equation 1)}$$

Where

dM = Change in the amount of drug released per unit area

dh = Change in the thickness of the zone of matrix that has been depleted of drug

Co = Total amount of drug in a unit volume of matrix

Cs = Saturated concentration of the drug within the matrix.

Additionally, according to diffusion theory:

$$dM = (Dm \cdot Cs / h) \cdot dt \text{ (Equation 2)}$$

Where:

Dm = Diffusion coefficient in the matrix.

h = Thickness of the drug-depleted matrix

dt = Change in time

By combining equation 1 and equation 2 and integrating:

$$M = [Cs \cdot Dm \cdot (2Co - Cs) \cdot t]^{1/2} \text{ (Equation 3)}$$

When the amount of drug is in excess of the saturation concentration, then:

$$M = [2Cs \cdot Dm \cdot Co \cdot t]^{1/2} \text{ (Equation 4)}$$

Equation 3 and equation 4 relate the amount of drug release to the square-root of time. Therefore, if a system is predominantly diffusion controlled, then it is expected that a plot of the drug release vs. square root of time will result in a straight line. Drug release from a porous monolithic matrix involves the simultaneous penetration of surrounding liquid, dissolution of drug and leaching out of the drug through tortuous interstitial channels and pores^{25,26}. The volume and length of the openings must be accounted for in the drug release from a porous or granular matrix:

$$M = [Ds \cdot Ca \cdot p / T \cdot (2Co - p \cdot Ca) t]^{1/2} \text{ (Equation 5)}$$

Where:

p = Porosity of the matrix

t = Tortuosity

Ca = solubility of the drug in the release medium

Ds = Diffusion coefficient in the release medium.

T = Diffusional pathlength

For pseudo steady state, the equation can be written as:

$$M = [2D \cdot Ca \cdot Co (p/T)t]^{1/2} \text{ (Equation 6)}$$

The total porosity of the matrix can be calculated with the following equation:

$$p = pa + Ca / \rho + Cex / pex \text{ (Equation 7)}$$

Where:

p = Porosity

ρ = Drug density

pa = Porosity due to air pockets in the matrix

pex = Density of the water soluble excipients

Cex = Concentration of water soluble excipients

For the purpose of data treatment, equation 7 can be reduced to:

$$M = k \cdot t^{1/2} \text{ (Equation 8)}$$

Where k is a constant, so that the amount of drug released versus the square root of time will be linear, if the release of drug from matrix is diffusion-controlled. If this is the case, the release of drug from a homogeneous matrix system can be controlled by varying the following parameters:

- Initial concentration of drug in the matrix
- Porosity
- Tortuosity
- Polymer system forming the matrix
- Solubility of the drug.

Bimodal Release

In certain systems there is a bimodal or anomalous release of the active ingredient. In these systems there is diffusion; additionally, the extended release polymer may become hydrated and begin to dissolve leading to release upon erosion. These systems are complex and difficult to mathematically model since the diffusional path length undergoes change due to the polymer dissolution^{27,28}.

A series of transport phenomena are involved in the release of a drug from a swellable, diffusion/erodible matrix:

- a.) Initially, there are steep water concentration gradients at the polymer/water interface, resulting in absorption of water into the matrix.
- b.) Due to the absorption of water, the polymer swells, resulting in dramatic changes of drug and polymer concentration, increasing the dimensions of the system and increasing macromolecular mobility.
- c.) Upon contact with water the drug dissolves and diffuses out of the device.
- d.) With increasing water content, the diffusion coefficient of the drug increase substantially.
- e.) In the case of a poorly water-soluble drug, dissolved and undissolved drug coexist within the polymer matrix
- f.) Finally, the polymer itself dissolves. These systems are described in terms of fronts.

The following fronts have been defined, with regard to anomalous release systems:

- The “swelling front”, the erosion front, and the diffusion front. The swelling front separates the rubbery region (swelling polymer area) which has enough water absorbed within the polymer to lower the Tg of the polymer below the respective environmental temperature allowing for macromolecular mobility and swelling, from the non-swelling polymer region (where the polymer exhibits a Tg that is above the respective environmental temperature).

- The “erosion front” separates the matrix from the bulk solution and is the interface between the unstirred layer with polymer concentration gradient and the well stirred medium.

- The “diffusion front” is between the swelling and erosion front and separated the areas of non dissolved drug from the area of dissolved drug.

With regard to swelling matrix systems, alternate models have been proposed to describe the diffusion, swelling, and dissolution processes occurring with into the system and these phenomena lead to drug release.

The gel strength is important in the matrix performance and is controlled by the concentration, viscosity and chemical structure of the rubbery polymer. This restricts the suitability of the hydrophilic polymers for preparation of swellable matrices. Polymers such as carboxymethylcellulose, hydroxypropylcellulose or tragacanth gums do not form the gel layer quickly. Consequently, they are not recommended as excipients to be used alone in swellable matrices²⁹. In 1985 Peppas introduced a semi-empirical equation describing the drug release behaviour from anomalous-release, hydrophilic matrix systems:

$$Q = k t^n \text{ (Equation 9)}$$

Where:

Q = Fraction of drug release in time (t)

t = Time

k = Rate constant (incorporates characteristics of polymer system and drug)

n = Diffusional exponent

The value of n is indicative of the drug release mechanism.

In order to describe relaxational transport, then modified equation 9 in order to account for relaxational transport:

$$Q = k_1 \cdot t^n + k_2 \cdot t^{2n} \quad (\text{Equation 10})$$

Where:

k_1 = Fickian diffusion constant

k_2 = Relaxational mechanism constant

If the surface area of the system is fixed, which is unlikely, the value of n should be 0.5 and equation 10 is transformed to:

$$Q = k_1 \cdot t^{0.5} + k_2 \cdot t \quad (\text{Equation 11})$$

The first term of this equation accounts for diffusional phenomena, while the second term of this equation accounts for polymer erosion.

Diagrammatic representation of drug release according to Higuchi model

APPROACHES IN THE DESIGN OF MATRIX SYSTEMS

Various approaches are present in the design of matrix systems, and are classified as follows.

Approaches in the design of matrix systems

Hydrophobic		Hydrophilic	
Swellable	Swellable and erodable	Erodable/Digestible	Non-erodable/ Non-digestible
Free swelling	Restricted swelling	Non-porous (Homogeneous)	Porous (Heterogenous)
		Dissolved drug	Dispersed drug

Conclusion

This review has elaborated matrix system, advantages and disadvantages of matrix systems, polymers used and release mechanism from the matrix system. By studying various polymers, it is concluded that ether cellulose polymers

(especially HPMC), on account of its specific characteristics, have been used largely in hydrophilic matrices and non biodegradable polymers like ethyl cellulose and waxes are used

for oral controlled-release systems that can be developed for solid dosage forms³⁰.

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20110030201196202